

Coaching Proficiency and Efficacy of Coaches in Sporting Activities

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Abstract: This study is aimed to find out the relationship between coaching proficiency and the efficacy of coaches in sporting activities. This study utilized the non-experimental quantitative research design using descriptive technique involving teachers in Malita District of Davao Occidental Division, Philippines. The study was conducted on the second semester of School Year 2024-2025. Research instruments on coaching proficiency and the efficacy of coaches in sporting activities were used as source of data. Using mean and pearson-r as statistical tools to treat the data, the study showed the following results: the study found to exhibit a very high level of coaching proficiency, there is a very high level of efficacy of coaches in sporting activities, there is a significant relationship between coaching proficiency and the efficacy of coaches in sporting activities. This implies that the higher the coaching proficiency, the higher is the efficacy of coaches in sporting activities. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between coaching proficiency and the efficacy of coaches in sporting activities was rejected.

Keywords: coaching proficiency, efficacy of coaches, porting activities, school administration and supervision.

I. INTRODUCTION

The world of sports put a high premium on efficacy of coaches in the competitive arena of sports as this is particularly crucial in terms of creating a positive outcome in any sports event. Interestingly, regardless of the number of trainings coaches have underwent in their coaching stints, their efficacy in the field of sport coaching is yet to be developed as manifested in their poor understanding of the individual athlete's personality and how to best motivate these athletes remain a top concern not to mention their lack of skills in recognizing the value of team dynamics in winning in the sports competition (Collins & Collins, 2015).

Meanwhile, managerial coaching competencies are desirable attribute of coaches as these are best ways to help correct and improve the inefficiency and poor performance of coaches in sporting activities. Addressing this ineffectiveness oftentimes help coaches to deliver their basic functions and ultimately link individual effectiveness of athletes with team performance (Beattie, Kim, Hagen, Egan, Ellinger & Hamlin, 2014).

In school, the inefficiency of coaches in performing their tasks is evident in their failure to help athletes maintain confidence in themselves. Once the athletes show poor performance in their sport, the coach tends to threaten the athletes to delay water breaks and even shout at them in the presence of other athletes instead of motivating them to perform their best. These cause humiliation and affect the self-esteem of the athletes as the acts do more harm than good (Norman, 2014).

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At the time of the study, the researcher has rarely come across of researches that dealt on the influence of managerial coaching competencies of coaches on their efficacy in coaching sporting events as this will help coaches and other beneficiary of this study to design training and improve in terms of coaching in sporting activities, hence the rationale of the conduct of this study.

II. BODY OF ARTICLE

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to determine the relationship between the coaching proficiency and the efficacy of coaches in sporting activities. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of coaching proficiency in terms of:
 - 1.1. coaching mindset;
 - 1.2. building trusting relationships;
 - 1.3. effective coaching interaction, and
 - 1.4. performance management and enhancement?
2. What is the level of efficacy of coaches in sporting activities in terms of:
 - 2.1 motivation;
 - 2.2 game strategy;
 - 2.3 technique, and
 - 2.4 character-building?
3. Is there a significant relationship between coaching proficiency and the efficacy of coaches in sporting activities.

Hypothesis

The following hypotheses will be treated at 0.05 level of significance.

There is no significant relationship between coaching proficiency and the efficacy of coaches in sporting activities.

III. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized a quantitative correlational design is a type of non-experimental research design used to determine whether and to what degree a relationship exists between two or more quantifiable variables. This study will find out the significance of the relationship between coaching proficiency and the efficacy of coaches in sporting activities.

Statistical Treatment

The following statistical tools were used in the analysis of data.

Mean. This was used to determine the level of coaching proficiency and the efficacy of coaches in sporting activities.

Pearson *r*. This was used to determine the significance of the relationship between coaching proficiency and the efficacy of coaches in sporting activities.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Level of Coaching Proficiency of Coaches

Shown in Table 1 is the level coaching proficiency of coaches with an overall mean of 4.19 with a descriptive equivalent of very high indicating that all enumerated indicators were oftentimes observed. The overall mean was the result obtained from the mean of the indicators for the specific items from the questionnaire intended for this particular indicator which was appended in this study.

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Among the enumerated indicators, performance management and enhancement has the highest mean rating with a mean score of 4.25 or very high, coaching mindset, 4.22 or very high, building trusting relationship, 4.14 or very high, and effective coaching interaction, 4.18 or very high.

The result of this study is in congruence with the views of Courson, Goldenberg, Adams, Anderson, Colgate, Cooper & Klossner (2014) who pointed out that the managerial coaching competencies of coaches determine how knowledgeable coaches are in terms of their capacity to apply their knowledge and beliefs in coaching. It is also the proficiency of coaches in terms of delivering their professional competence in the field of coaching education. On the other hand, while managerial coaching competence displays the skill of coaches. It shows what specific competence that coaches need to improve for a more effective practice and to understand what they still need to be able to do with what they already knew.

Table I. Level of Coaching Proficiency of Coaches

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Levels
Coaching Mindset	4.22	Very High
Building Trusting Relationship	4.14	Very High
Effective Coaching Interaction	4.18	Very High
Performance Management and Enhancement	4.25	Very High
Overall	4.19	Very High

Level of Efficacy of Coaches in Sporting Activities

Shown in Table 2 is the level of efficacy of coaches in sporting events with an overall mean of 4.18 with a descriptive equivalent of very high indicating that all enumerated indicators were oftentimes observed. The overall mean was the result obtained from the mean of the indicators for the specific items from the questionnaire intended for this particular indicator which was appended in this study.

Among the enumerated indicators, character building has the highest mean rating with a mean score of 4.28 or very high, motivation, 4.16 or very high, game strategy, 4.18 or very high, and technique, 4.17 or very high.

Table II. Level of Efficacy of Coaches in Sporting Activities

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Levels
Motivation	4.16	Very High
Game Strategy	4.18	Very High
Technique	4.17	Very High
Character Building	4.24	Very High
Overall	4.18	Very High

The result of the study is in consonance with the findings of Rylander (2015) who averred that in the competitive world of sports, athletes are often in the spotlight, celebrated for their talent, strength, and perseverance. However, behind every successful athlete or team stands a coach whose role is just as crucial. The efficacy of coaches in sporting events is a key factor that directly influences athletic performance, team cohesion, and overall success. A coach's ability to prepare, motivate, and lead athletes can make the difference between victory and defeat.

The result of this study is also aligned with the finding of Jones, Edwards, and Viotto Filho (2016) who stressed that the efficacy of coaches in sporting events encompasses preparation, strategy, motivation, communication, emotional

intelligence, and leadership. Coaches play a pivotal role in shaping athletic performance and team success. Their influence extends beyond the scoreboard, impacting the personal and professional development of athletes. As such, investing in coaching education, support, and recognition is essential to the advancement of sports and the athletes who participate in them.

Significance on the Relationship between Coaching Proficiency and Efficacy of Coaches in Sporting Activities

Illustrated in Table 3 were the results of the test of relationship between variables involved in the study. The overall correlation had a computed value of 0.106 with a probability value of $p < 0.01$ which is significant at 0.05 level. Hence the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between coaching proficiency and the efficacy of coaches in sporting activities is rejected.

The result of the study is in congruence with the statement of Bean, Forneris, and Brunet (2016) who believed that the relationship between coaching proficiency and the efficacy of coaches in sporting activities is deeply interconnected, as a coach's proficiency directly influences their capacity to bring out the best in their athletes both on and off the field.

Table III. Significance on the Relationship between Teacher Communication Behavior and Student Engagement

Pair	Variables	Correlation Coefficient	p-value	Decision on Ho
IV and DV	Coaching Proficiency and Efficacy of Coaches in Sporting Activities	0.106	0.000	Reject

The result of the study is supported by the statement of Fransen, Decroos, Vanbeselaere, Vande Broek, De Cuyper, Vanroy & Boen (2015) who believe that the relationship between coaching proficiency and the efficacy of coaches in sporting activities is fundamental. Coaching proficiency serves as the backbone of a coach's effectiveness, enabling them to train, inspire, and lead athletes toward success. When coaches are knowledgeable, skilled, and emotionally intelligent, they are more likely to deliver meaningful results, build strong relationships, and make lasting contributions to their athletes' performance and character development. Therefore, enhancing coaching proficiency is not just a professional requirement, it is a pathway to becoming a truly effective and transformative coach.

V. CONCLUSION

Based from the findings of the study, conclusions are drawn in this section. The study found to exhibit a very high level of coaching proficiency of coaches. This means that the provisions relating to coaching proficiency of coaches is always manifested.

The study revealed a very high level of efficacy of coaches in sporting events. This indicates that the provisions relating to efficacy of coaches in sporting events are embodied in the item is always manifested.

The results of the study also confirm that there is a significant relationship between coaching proficiency and the efficacy of coaches in sporting activities. This implies that the higher the coaching proficiency, the higher is the efficacy of coaches in sporting activities. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between coaching proficiency and the efficacy of coaches in sporting activities was rejected.

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